

Wide-Bandgap Materials for High-Intensity Wireless Laser Power Transmission in the Solar System

Manuel Peralta-Fuentes, Florencia Almonacid and Eduardo F. Fernández

Abstract—High-Intensity Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) is emerging as a ground-breaking technology with a wide range of promising applications, such as space exploration missions. While conventional photovoltaic devices primarily rely on GaAs-based converters, they present significant efficiency losses under high-intensity scenarios. This work explores the potential of novel wide-bandgap semiconductors, specifically SiCs and InGaN, to outperform traditional technologies. We conduct a comprehensive theoretical analysis of these materials as laser power converters across planetary atmospheres of the Solar System. Results indicate that InGaN and SiC-based converters could achieve efficiencies exceeding 75% in high potential candidates, with very tenuous atmospheres, such as the Moon or Mercury. For planets and satellites with Earth-like atmospheres, the efficiencies of these materials could be beyond 50%. In all cases, the novel, wide bandgap materials seem to outperform GaAs. These results highlight the suitability of wide-bandgap materials for WLPT paving the way for reliable and continuous in future and space exploration missions.

Index Terms— Photovoltaics, Semiconductor devices, SiCs and InGaN, Space exploration, Wireless laser power transmission.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-INTENSITY Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) is a rapidly evolving technology, with a growth on investment, the industrial ecosystem, and academic publications and congresses during the last decades [1], [2]. It consists on the use of monochromatic light sources to transfer power to remote systems without physical or electrical connections involved [3]. This is accomplished using photovoltaic (PV) devices, usually called laser power converters (LPCs), which are optimized to transform the input laser intensity into electricity. This emerging technology has the potential to transform the way energy is transmitted and utilized in a vast number of applications that range from the Earth’s atmosphere and underwater environments, to high-risk areas, such as aircrafts, nuclear or fuel plants [4].

The technology becomes even more critical for in-space

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applications, where the implementation of wiring is not feasible. In this case, WLPT could open the path to the exploration of celestial bodies, such as planets and satellites. For instance, it could be implemented to power rovers or ground receivers through Space Solar Power Satellites (SSPS) [5], or to charge aircrafts or satellites from energy power stations in the surface of the bodies [6], [7].

Under these circumstances, the coupling between the LPCs and the atmospheric absorption of the planets and satellites becomes crucial to maximize the overall WLPT efficiency. This has been pointed out in previous works by the authors, concerning the selection of optimal transmission wavelengths on Earth [8] and underwater [9]. However, to the date, the optimum bandgap and LPC materials for the main bodies of the Solar System still remains unknown.

This letter presents the first study to select the wavelength ranges, and potential novel materials, for WLPT according to the spectral transmittances of all planets and relevant satellites of the Solar System. In this sense, a survey of celestial bodies is performed, studying their atmospheric transmittances, and classifying them according to their potential. Based on this, and on the methodology previously introduced by the authors, the optimal spectral ranges, and related PV materials, are proposed to overcome the state-of-the-art GaAs-based technology. The final aim is to promote WLPT as a key enable technology to facilitate the Solar System exploration.

II. METHODOLOGY

The overall methodology is analogous to the previously used by the authors [8], [9]. The LPC efficiency (η_{LPC}) is calculated using the Shockley-Queisser formulation [8]. Hence, the external quantum efficiency (EQE) is considered ideal (EQE = 1), radiative as the only recombination mechanism, and the wavelength of the laser (λ_{laser}) equal to the bandgap (E_{gap}) of the LPC: $\lambda_{laser} = hc/E_{gap}$. In this case, the value of the series resistance (R_s) is fixed at $10^{-2} \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$, matching with a realistic scenario of high-efficiency LPCs, and to account to the main source of non-intrinsic conversion losses under high-intensity input irradiance.

The relationship between the incident power on the LPC ($\Phi_{in}(\lambda)$), and the power of the source ($\Phi_s(\lambda)$), is given by the well-known Beer-Lambert law: $\Phi_{in}(\lambda) = \Phi_s \cdot T(\lambda)$. In this study, Φ_s is fixed at a standard realistic value of 100 W cm^{-2} . The atmospheric transmittance ($T(\lambda)$) of each planet or satellite has been computed using NASA’s tool, “Planetary Spectrum Generator” (PSG) [10], in a spectral range of interest between 200 and 2000 nm. The configuration to obtain $T(\lambda)$ corresponds to an observer on the surface of the object, looking up with no deviation angle. This guarantees

that the atmosphere of each body is traversed completely, once and perpendicularly, corresponding to AM (Air Mass) = 1. Finally, the global WLPT efficiency (η_{global}) is computed by applying the PV model to the incident power of the laser on the LPC after considering the $T(\lambda)$ value each atmosphere ($\eta_{\text{global}}(\Phi_{\text{in}}, T) = \eta_{\text{LPC}}(\Phi_{\text{in}}) \cdot T(\lambda)$).

III. RESULTS

A. Survey and overview of celestial bodies

As previously mentioned, the first step is to define the targets of this study regarding potential candidates for WLPT in the Solar System. A survey including all planets and the most relevant satellites is conducted, separating the candidates in three categories. The results are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE I
SURVEY OF PLANETS AND SATELLITES OF THE
SOLAR SYSTEM

Potential for WLPT	Object name	Atmospheric properties
High	The Moon	Very weak and tenuous atmospheres, with no significant collisional interaction [11], [12], [13]. Transmittance spectra equal to 1, equivalent to the vacuum
	Mercury	
	Galilean Moons (Ganymede, Callisto, Io, and Europa)	
Medium	The Earth	Intermediate, Earth-like atmospheres, variable transmittances in the wavelength range of interest
	Mars	
	Venus	
	Titan	
	Triton	
Low	Jupiter	Very thick and highly absorbing atmospheres, with abundant methane, sulfate, and ice clouds [14], [15]. Transmittance equal to 0
	Neptune	
	Uranus	
	Saturn	

The atmospheres of high potential candidates, such as the Moon or Mercury, have $T(\lambda) = 1$, which is analogous to the vacuum in free space environments. Therefore, their WLPT efficiencies are only affected by the E_{gap} of the LPC and the related R_s losses. η_{global} is greater for wide bandgap materials, as a larger bandgap reduces the proportion of intrinsic and extrinsic losses generated during the absorption and emission of radiation [16]. In contrast, low potential objects, notably gas and ice giants, present zero transmittances, becoming not valid for the WLPT scenario proposed in this work. Finally, the atmospheres of medium potential candidates, with $T(\lambda)$ values from 0 to 1 in the range of interest, need to be carefully analyzed to identify the most efficient wavelength windows. Fig. 1 presents an overview of the atmospheric transmittances of the medium potential candidates.

Fig. 1. Atmospheric transmittances of the medium potential candidates.

B. WLPT efficiencies and materials

The obtained η_{global} values for the high and medium potential candidates, separately, are shown in Fig. 2. This figure highlights the wavelengths corresponding to the bandgaps¹ of two promising wide E_{gap} materials for LPC devices: Si-C polytypes [17] and the InGaN alloy [18], in comparison with GaAs, a widely implemented semiconductor.

Regarding Fig. 2 (top), the Si-C polytypes that present greater efficiencies are 4H and 6H-SiC, above 70% for the candidates with weak atmospheres. This result is matched by GaN (without In content). For Mars, the efficiency is decreased, but the choice of materials is the same. However, the use of 3C-SiC and InGaN with a low In fraction could also be viable without a significant loss in efficiency. In all cases, these wide bandgap semiconductors theoretically outperform GaAs.

In the bottom part of Fig. 2, for Earth and Titan, with similar atmospheres, 3C is as efficient as 6C-SiC, slightly outperforming 4H-SiC. For the InGaN alloy, the peak efficiency is matched when a small In composition is included. Titan is one of the most interesting targets of space exploration in the Solar System, as it is the only known object with oceans on its surface, other than the Earth [19]. Finally, for Venus, WLPT would only be possible within the wavelength window between 800 and 1200 nm that has also been pointed out by other authors [20]. Furthermore, it has lower transmittance values than the rest of medium potential candidates, leading to efficiencies below 20%. SiCs are not suitable for WLPT in Venus, but the bandgap of InGaN matches the window if In compositions are above 0.5. However, its fabrication with very high In contents is still challenging, due to significant losses on material quality [21].

¹ The Si-C polytypes' bandgaps are 366 nm for 4H, 400 nm for 6H and 525 nm for 3C. The bandgap of $\text{In}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x\text{N}$ is given by the bowing equation $E_{\text{gap}} = 3.42x + 0.7(1-x) - 1.43x(1-x)$. The bandgap of GaAs is 873 nm [8].

Fig. 2. Efficiencies of high potential candidates, Mars and Triton (top), and Earth, Venus and Titan (bottom). Vertical lines indicate the E_{gap} wavelengths of SiCs, InGaN and GaAs.

Finally, Table 2 summarizes the efficiencies corresponding to the best SiC polytype, the optimal InGaN, according to the In content, and the GaAs for each candidate.

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF WLPT EFFICIENCIES AND MATERIALS IN THE SOLAR SYSTEM

Object	SiC	InGaN	GaAs
Earth	57.1 % (3C-SiC)	59.0 % ($\text{In}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{N}$)	29.5 %
Mars	43.3 % (4H-SiC)	43.4 % (GaN)	23.7 %
Titan	58.2 % (6H-SiC)	60.3 % ($\text{In}_{0.18}\text{Ga}_{0.82}\text{N}$)	29.5 %
Triton	76.3 % (4H-SiC)	76.6 % (GaN)	29.5 %
Venus	(-)	12.9 % ($\text{In}_{0.71}\text{Ga}_{0.29}\text{N}$)	0.7 %
HP	76.3 % (4H-SiC)	76.6 % (GaN)	29.5 %

IV. CONCLUSION

This work investigates for the first time the wavelengths and potential materials to optimize Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) in planets and satellites of the Solar

System. The global efficiency is modelled using the Shockley-Queisser formulation in combination with the spectral atmospheric properties obtained using NASA's Planetary Spectrum Generator, using a methodology previously developed by the working group. As a case of study, WLPT efficiencies are computed under state-of-the-art conditions: 100 W cm^{-2} as the power of the source and $10^{-2} \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ as the series resistance of the laser power converters (LPCs).

Results show that novel wide-bandgap semiconductors, such as SiC and InGaN, are promising and offer an alternative to conventional materials with narrow bandgaps, such as GaAs. For high potential candidates with very weak atmospheres, such as Mercury and the Moon, GaN and 4H-SiC achieve peak efficiencies exceeding 75%. For medium potential targets, SiCs and InGaN with low In contents exhibit efficiencies around 60% in Earth and Titan, and above 40% in Mars. For Venus, InGaN is one of the few viable materials capable of enabling WLPT through its atmosphere, even though the required composition is challenging to fabricate.

In summary, this work opens the path to wide-bandgap LPCs and the WLPT technology in the Solar System, broadening its potential for space exploration. Future work should extend this initial attempt by incorporating a more detailed model that accounts for the specific material properties, recombination mechanisms, and non-ideal effects of the LPCs proposed.

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